

THE IMPORTANCE OF SOCIAL ISSUES AT THE SAMARKAND SUMMIT OF THE SHANGHAI COOPERATION ORGANIZATION

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Annotation: This article discusses the issues voiced at the regular Council of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization, which was held on September 15-16 this year in the city of Samarkand. The agreements signed by the member States of the organization and information about the importance of this organization are highlighted.

In particular, it describes the existence of many international organizations in the world and their types, including the structure, activities and specifics of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization.

Keywords: Shanghai Cooperation Organization, summit, economic cooperation, regional security.

It is known that there are many international organizations in the world, which are organized according to different goals, areas or regions. Therefore, they can be divided into several types depending on their legal organization.

- firstly, to international organizations that all countries can become members of;
- secondly, to international organizations established only in certain regions;
- thirdly, it can be divided into international organizations organized according to a sector or purpose.

Similarly, the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO) was established as a regional security and economic cooperation organization.

This organization was established on June 15, 2001 in the Chinese city of Shanghai with the participation of six countries, namely Kazakhstan, China, Kyrgyzstan, Russia, Tajikistan and Uzbekistan.

The main goal of the organization is to strengthen mutual trust and good neighborliness among member states and to establish effective cooperation in political, trade-economic, scientific-technical, cultural, as well as education, energy, transport, tourism, environmental protection and other fields.

In addition, ensuring regional security, joint fight against terrorism, extremism and separatism are among the main tasks of the organization.

In today's difficult and dangerous situation in the world, some thoughts were expressed about this organization. It should be noted that the Shanghai Cooperation Organization is not considered an international military organization from the legal point of view. This international organization is the largest regional organization in the world, covering a wide area in terms of geography and uniting about half of the population of the planet.

It is no exaggeration to say that this organization has shown its influence on the world scale during the past short period.

In particular, the SCO managed to establish practical cooperation in the fight against security issues, especially terrorism, extremism, separatism and drug trafficking, and became a full-fledged regional organization.

Also, in the new conditions of the world economy, great attention is paid to the development of the economic and social cooperation potential of the member states of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization.

Therefore, interest in the Shanghai Cooperation Organization is growing day by day, and the number of member States is increasing. Today, the members are China, India, Russia, Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan and Pakistan. Afghanistan, Belarus, Mongolia and Iran will participate as observer countries. Also,

the partner countries are: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Turkey, Cambodia, Sri Lanka and Nepal.

According to the procedures of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization, one of the member countries will chair it every year. This time it is Uzbekistan's turn to host the summit. In fact, the summit coincides with the time of the complex process taking place in the world, armed conflicts in different countries.

The President of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, in his article published on the eve of the SCO summit in Samarkand, noted that the system of international cooperation based on universal principles and norms is falling apart. President noted the "deep decline of trust at the global level" as one of the main reasons.

He also noted that Uzbekistan's presidency of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization coincided with a unique period of "historical evolution" in which intense processes are taking place on a global scale - a historical era is ending and a new era, which is difficult to predict, is beginning.

In fact, the actual legal results expected from the Samarkand summit, which is taking place at such a dangerous time, are peace and security in the region, cooperation in the economic and social spheres, strengthening of friendly relations, agreement on global solidarity, achievement of sustainable development, unification of common efforts and opportunities against any threats and dangers. consists of mobilization.

At the same time, it should be particularly noted that social issues, especially youth, tourism, culture, sports, have become one of the topical issues on the agenda.

In addition, within the framework of this summit, not only the official documents of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization, but also the participating countries managed to conclude mutual agreements. In the fields of trade, investment, logistics and transportation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, especially the railways of China, Kyrgyzstan and Uzbekistan, and railway traffic passing through Uzbekistan, Afghanistan, Pakistan, the relevant issues were resolved.

We are confident that the decisions made at the summit of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization will make a significant contribution to strengthening dialogue, mutual understanding and cooperation both at the regional and global levels.

As a result of the summit, a total of 44 documents were adopted – agreements, concepts, programs and other decisions. This is a record figure in the history of the organization.

Including:

- On a comprehensive action plan for the implementation of the provisions of the Treaty on Long-term Good-Neighborliness, Friendship and Cooperation of the SCO member States for 2023-2027;
- On the concept of the SCO member States on the development of interdependence and the creation of efficient transport corridors;
- On the Regulations on the honorary title of "SCO Goodwill Ambassador";
- On the "roadmap" for a gradual increase in the share of national currencies in the mutual settlements of the SCO member states;
- On the signing of a memorandum on Iran's obligations to obtain the status of a SCO member state;
- On the beginning of the process of admission of the Republic of Belarus to the SCO;
- On granting the Republic of Maldives, Bahrain, the United Arab Emirates, the Union Republic of Myanmar, Kuwait the status of a SCO dialogue partner;
- The announcement of the city of Varanasi (India) as the tourist and cultural capital of the SCO for 2022-2023;
- On the signing of a memorandum between the SCO Secretariat and the UN (UNESCO) on education, science and culture;

– On the reports of the SCO Secretary General on the activities of the organization over the past year, as well as on the activities of the Council of the SCO Regional Anti-Terrorist Structure for 2021;

– On the cancellation of the decisions of the SCO Council of Heads of State;

– Decisions have been made to improve the SCO's activities.

In addition, the following documents were signed during the event:

- the Council of Heads of SCO States:

– on the response to climate change;

– about global food security;

- statements on ensuring energy security have been adopted.